

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN MONGOLIA

Tuvd Dorj,

Academician Mongolian Academy of Sciences, doctor (Sc.D), Professor, Chairman of the Board of Directors of the Mongolian University Ulaanbaatar-Erdem

Avirmed Davaasuren

Doctor (Sc.D), Professor, Head of Department of Institute international studies Mongolian Academy of Sciences

Yavuukhulan Buddayan-Och

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Abstract

The prolonged global economic crisis and its increasing frequency have exacerbated the global geo-economic landscape. This has further destabilized Mongolia's political, social, and economic conditions, particularly as a small economy positioned between the major powers of Russia and China. As a result, Mongolia's economic structure increasingly undermines its sovereign independence, heightens dependence on external markets, impedes the modernization of its industrial sector, and restricts the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises. In the face of unfavorable geopolitical and geo-economic conditions, it has become clear that theoretical models of economic development that do not account for Mongolia's unique characteristics and specific realities are inadequate and ineffective. This significantly impedes the comprehensive resolution of underdevelopment across various sectors of industry and economy, alongside challenges such as outdated technology, the strengthening of national identity and spirit, fostering creativity, addressing the erosion of moral values, and tackling critical social issues, including unemployment, poverty, and environmental degradation.

The development and promotion of small and medium-sized enterprises in Mongolia has long been one of the most critical social and economic challenges. Despite numerous government initiatives aimed at supporting small and medium enterprises through legal, managerial, organizational and financial measures, tangible outcomes have yet to be realized. There is a clear and growing need to expand government support to establish a conducive environment for the viable development of small and medium enterprises.

In this context, we have undertaken a scientific study to examine the challenges associated with the development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The research focuses on analyzing the nature, content, criteria, and classification of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) based on industry characteristics, income levels, and employee numbers. The objective is to evaluate their contributions to the economy and to identify effective methods for enhancing their roles in economic growth.

To achieve this, we examined the experiences of various countries in classifying and defining small and medium-sized enterprises, distinguishing between the terms "business person" and "entrepreneur", and enhancing the theoretical concepts of micro, small, and medium enterprises across different economic sectors.

Keywords: European Union, International Labor Organization, small and medium-sized enterprises, services, entrepreneurs, herdsman, farmers, etc.

1. Theoretical issues of small and medium-sized businesses

Small and medium-sized enterprises have been defined differently by scholars from various theoretical schools in the scientific literature and publications worldwide. These definitions have evolved over time, reflecting the unique characteristics of geographical location, climate conditions, levels of production and human development. Advancement in technical and technological capabilities, the balance between production and consumption within the economy, market size, economic capacity, and the overall level of socio-economic development.

Based on an analysis of definitions from both international and local scholars, it can be concluded that a business person is an individual who independently owns the means of production, demonstrates innovation, creativity, actively participates in economic activities, competes in the market to generate income, assumes risks, and takes responsibility for his venture.

First and foremost, business person must have the freedom to operate economically. In other words, minimal government intervention in business activities enhances the profitability of enterprises, which in turn, benefits society as a whole. This fosters greater commitment new capabilities. To achieve this, it is essential that the current legal framework ensures the protection of business freedoms.

The future success of businesses will be significantly influenced by the availability and provision of reliable data. Additionally, the modern business person must possess advanced skills in organizing, managing both service and production in a highly competitive environment, while fostering key qualities such as goal orientation and commitment. The business concept is

closely linked to sustaining financial independence, ensuring overall well-being, and generating consistent income and profits¹.

Figure 1. General characteristics of an SME owner

Source: The authors' work is based on the compilation of research

According to Figure 1, herders in rural areas engage in a risky business due to its reliance on nature conditions and weather, as noted by R. Cantillon. They develop organizational skills through the inheritance of livestock husbandry practices from their ancestors, as observed by F.Walker. These herders, who are both land and livestock owners (A.Smith), act as managers (A.Marshall) capable of maintaining the unity of production means and resources (J.B Say). They also serve as owners of the means and resources for livestock production (J.Schumpeter) and possess the knowledge and skills necessary to lead the livestock business, while bearing responsibility for their assets and generating profits through expansion of livestock numbers (P.Drucker).

However, according to J.B. Say, herders do not qualify as industrial entrepreneurs, as they place less emphasis on practices such as animal branding and selective breeding. They are less inclined toward innovation or the 'creative destruction' of traditional methods of production, and do not operate within a highly competitive environment.

As noted by A. Kaminski, this type of business does not involve cooperation or the exchange of means of production. Instead, it is characterized by self-motivation, a focus on survival, and a lack of time constraints. In this context, herders skillfully manage livestock husbandry by leveraging weather forecasting to adapt to changing environmental conditions. A review of the latest publications by scholars reveals the use of

various terms to describe business activities, including 'business', 'small and medium enterprises', and 'micro and medium-sized businesses' all referring to the same phenomenon.

The term 'small and medium enterprises (SMEs)' has become an increasingly prominent concept among international researchers, economists, and policymakers. This growing interest highlights the importance of studying small and medium enterprises', particularly their role in the economic growth of specific industries, development trends, and the subsequent need for comprehensive data in this field of research.

In the economic context of Mongolia, an entrepreneur can be identified as an individual with aspiration, ambition, motivation and innovative thinking, who is willing to take risks associated with their property, accept responsibility, and independently pursue economic gains.

Therefore, entrepreneurs in Mongolia can be considered to range from individuals engaged in livestock husbandry and agriculture to those conducting private small businesses, and finally, to executives of large enterprises, regardless of ownership.

As a result of disciplined economic activities, herders produce animal-based raw materials and sell them. The income generated from these activities is used to purchase consumer goods for household needs. Although herders are not officially registered as entrepreneurs in official statistics, it is argued that they should be recognized and registered as entrepreneurs².

¹ Даваасурэн А. Становление предпринимательства в регионах Монголии: монография / Под. ред. д-ра экон. наук, профессора В.И.Самарухи. – Иркутск :Изд-во БГУЭП, 2013. – 219 с.

² Davaasuren A. Formation of entrepreneurship in the regions of Mongolia: monograph / A. Davaasuren; under. ed. Doctor of Economics Sciences, Professor V.I. Samarukhi. – Irkutsk: Publishing house BGUEP, 2013. – 219 p.

According to statistics, 49.9 percent of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating in urban areas are officially registered in the state register and are engaged in the commerce industry.

Additionally, 21.8 percent operate in the service sector, while the remaining 28.3 percent are involved in the manufacturing industry³.

As income and capital accumulation increase, entrepreneurs tend to shift from the commerce sector to the manufacturing industry, thereby becoming industrial entrepreneurs. It is important to note that this transition requires a solid understanding of management, as well as the ability to think on a larger scale. To address these needs, it becomes essential for entrepreneurs to collaborate with potential partners and experts.

Although various economic theories distinguish between small and medium-sized businesses and entrepreneurs, both economic factors (such as production, private and state or foreign ownership, capital combination, and economic profit) and psychological and intellectual factors (such as initiative, responsibility, innovation, and motivation in production and technology localization) encompass similar qualities that contribute to their success.

Business or entrepreneurship is a relatively new research field that holds significant importance for the social and economic development of any nation. We conclude that modern entrepreneurship is an independent area of study characterized by well-organized, innovative, and economic practices. Its primary focus is on activities aimed at income generation, under the ownership responsibility of one's own capital, within a risky environment.

2. International and Mongolian classification of small and medium-sized enterprises.

Countries around the world classify small, medium, and large enterprises in various ways. Based on the number of employees, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are typically categorized into three main groups by international organizations such as the European Union, the International Labor Organization, and the International Cooperation and Development Organization. These organizations set criteria that reflect the level of workforce development within a country's industrial and economic sectors. The International Labor Organization (ILO) defines small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) as those with the smallest number of employees, whereas the European Union (EU) classifies them as medium-sized, and the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) categorizes them as having the highest number of employees.

This distinction is primarily due to the fact that many EU and OECD member countries are industrialized nations in Western Europe, which boast a substantial pool of highly skilled workers. Consequently, small and medium-sized enterprises in these regions are often capable of producing value-added products. The significance of this classification lies in its consideration of

workforce capabilities. In essence, SMEs in EU countries predominantly refer to businesses operating within the industrial sector.

The International Labor Organization (ILO) encompasses not only industrialized countries but also the least developed nations. As such, it includes small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) across various sectors, ranging from individual entrepreneurs with minimal staff to legal entities. This classification, regardless of the type of activity, reflects the broad scope of SMEs as defined by the ILO.

Countries worldwide classify small and medium-sized enterprises differently, based on their socio-economic development, the level of industrialization, and the number of employees. These classifications utilize a range of criteria, including the number of employees, income, and asset volume, which vary according to the specific characteristics of each nation's economy.

Since the 17th century, the definition of an entrepreneur and entrepreneurship, along with their nature, has evolved significantly. In the context of economic freedom and competition, these concepts have been enriched with new characteristics and meanings over time.

First and foremost, it is essential to distinguish and understand two different concepts—industry and service. Production encompasses a wide range of activities, including research, testing, invention, implementation, and localization of technologies, as well as the development of these technologies. It also involves the creation, storage, use, production, and sale of raw materials and resources, including financial and human resources. The process of production is a complex one that entails planning, management, organization, supervision, and reporting, ultimately leading to the creation of the final product. In other words, it refers to the entire process involved in bringing any product to fruition.

Service is a more specific concept, encompassing all types of services provided during the pre-production and post-production stages. This includes areas such as finance, insurance, storage, communications, transportation, logistics, border and customs control, inspection, marketing, sales, and after-sales support, among others. These two concepts—industry and service—are mutually exclusive, each representing distinct aspects of the production and business process.

In Mongolia, the concepts of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are often confused. Specifically, family farms or home-based crafts are frequently referred to as SMEs. As a result, there is a need for the government to implement special policies to support these groups, which are not officially registered as legal entities and typically employ 2-5 individuals. These entities should be classified as micro-enterprises and service providers, with appropriate policies tailored to their unique needs.

Mongolia lacks prior experience in determining the classification of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by sector, and there is an urgent need to establish such classifications. To foster the development of micro and home-based production, as well as

³ Statistical Yearbook of the National Statistical Committee of Mongolia 2022, Classification of economic activities of

small and medium-sized enterprises and legal entities providing services, p. 751

small and medium-sized enterprises, it is crucial to implement targeted government policies and regulations. These should include optimal regulation of budgets,

taxes, finance, credit, and investment, tailored to the specific needs of each category of enterprise.

Table 2.

Classification of small and medium-sized enterprises in Mongolia

№	Sector by economic activity	Criteria	Household or micro		Small	Medium
			Small	Medium		
1	Agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector	Number of employees	3-5		5-9	10-15
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 200		200-500	500-1 billion
2	Manufacturing sector	Number of employees	10		10-20	20-50
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 200		200-300	300-500
3	Mining sector	Number of employees	...		10-50	50-100
		Operating income, (million MNT)	...		300 -1,5 billion	1,5-2,5 billion to
4	Construction industry	Number of employees	Up to 20		20-50	50-200
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 400		400-800	800-1,5 billion
5	Wholesale and retail sector	Number of employees	3-10		10-15	15-50
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 150		150-300	300-500
6	Transport and logistics sector	Number of employees	3-5		5-10	10-15
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 200		200-500	500 -1 billion
7	Electricity, gas, steam, ventilation, water supply, garbage, waste and cleaning activity	Number of employees	5		5-10	10-30
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 300		300-1 billion	1-1,5 billion
8	Information and communication sector	Number of employees	Up to 10		10-15	15-50
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 300		300-1 billion	1-2,5 billion
9	Financial and insurance services industry	Number of employees	Up to 10		10-20	20-50
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 400		400-800	800-1,5 billion
10	Hotels, apartments, apartments and catering services	Number of employees	Up to 10		10-30	30-50
		Operating income, (million MNT)	Up to 300		300-900	900 -1,5 billion

Note: The classification for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) was created by Sc.D. A. Davaasuren, reflecting the sector-based SME classifications used by foreign countries.

Source: Revision of the Law "Support of Small and Medium Enterprises and Services", approved by Parliament on June 6, 2019, <https://legalinfo.mn/mn/detail/14525>, Report of the Financial Service based on the results of 2022. Mongolia Regulatory Commission Financial Statements of Non-Banking Financial Institutions, September, Bank of Mongolia Banking Industry Financial Stability Report 2022, www.mongolbank.mn, China SME Sector Classification 中小会电别型最名电影, Revised 2017 d. Based on the documents, a classification of the small and medium-sized industry sector was created based on the population of Mongolia, market capacity, economic structure, industrial and labor development, per capita income and purchasing power of citizens.

In the Mongolian economy, sectors such as mining and extractive industries, commerce, finance, insurance, hospitality, housing, eatery, and rental services account for a significant share, while sectors like construction, agricultural crop production, processing, road transportation, logistics, and warehousing remain comparatively smaller. Given these circumstances, there are likely variations in income levels and the number of employees among micro or household-based businesses and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating in these different sectors.

The Law on Small and Medium Enterprises and Services Promotion of Mongolia classifies businesses as "micro enterprises and service providers," but it does not include home-based businesses or family artisans, and these entities are not recognized or legalized under the law.

On the other hand, Mongolian legal documents define small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) from a subjective perspective, but they do not provide definitions of SMEs or micro, small, and medium-sized en-

terprises (MSMEs) from a legal entity standpoint. Furthermore, there is no clear distinction between the concepts of SMEs and micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises, and there is no specific definition of manufacturing and services within the legal framework.

In the economic context of Mongolia, a "small and medium-sized entrepreneur" is an individual who possesses ambition, motivation, and initiative, demonstrating innovation and undertaking independent economic activities to generate profit, while assuming personal financial risk under the responsibility of private property. Therefore, regardless of whether these entrepreneurs are officially registered in the state register, they can include shepherds, farmers, family micro-entrepreneurs, and directors of large enterprises involved in livestock raising and agriculture in rural areas.

Conversely, the majority of small and medium-sized enterprises officially registered in the state register to operate in trade and various service sectors, with only a small proportion engaged in actual production. Most of these enterprises operate seasonally, primarily during the summer months. That is to say, the profits and income of most small and medium-sized enterprises in Mongolia are seasonal. This situation is influenced by several factors, including the country's geographical location, weather conditions, economic potential, the level of industrial and human development, technological advancements, the ratio of production to consumption, market capacity, and the extent of government involvement in the economy.

3. Conclusion

Small and medium-sized businesses and SMEs share similarities in theory, methodology, essence, and principles. However, the interpretations offered by both local and international scholars, as well as the definitions and classifications established by international organizations, vary to some extent.

The level of economic and social development, as well as the degree of industrialization within a country, significantly influences the factors determining the development of small and medium-sized enterprises. These factors include the level of productive forces, economic potential, market capacity, labor force development, and the income generated by SMEs. Additionally, the quantity, size, type, and areas of activity (whether in the export or domestic market) of the goods and products manufactured by SMEs are closely tied to these developmental aspects.

In our view, "business" is an extensive concept. We understand business as an economic activity in which an entrepreneur, whether independently or in collaboration with other entrepreneurs, engages in the production and sale of goods and services with the aim of increasing their own profits. This activity may occur

within any country and encompasses a wide range of entrepreneurial endeavors.

All types of business activities encompass a wide range of concepts, including raw materials, finished goods, products, food, machinery and equipment storage, transportation, production, export, import, marketing, consumption, and management. These elements are integral to the operation and success of businesses across various sectors. In the Mongolian context, business activities are primarily understood in terms of trade and services. While it is relatively straightforward to categorize an entrepreneur as a merchant, it is more challenging to classify them as a manufacturer. As a result, in practical terms, the concept of "small and medium-sized enterprises and services" has become relatively complex, encompassing various forms of business activities that extend beyond simple classifications.

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